

Accounting Education and Moral Competency of Accounting Students in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Moral competence serves as the bedrock of the accounting profession. This is critical for sustaining the profession's reputation and legitimacy. Due to the abundance of accounting scandals around the world during the past 20 years, its reputation and credibility have come under serious criticism. It was against this backdrop that this study examined the impact of accounting education on the moral competencies of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design based on the Deontology theory whereby open-ended ethical scenario-based questionnaire were distributed to 175 HND 2 accounting students in order to collect information on their perceptions of accounting education at the Polytechnic in order to measure their moral competencies. Cronbach alpha of 0.81 for both questionnaires demonstrated their reliability as data collection instruments. Data on accounting education was also collected through a close-ended questionnaire survey of 12 accounting lecturers at the Polytechnic. Descriptive statistics was employed to analyse the demographic data of the respondents while multiple regression analysis was used to test the study's hypotheses. The ANOVA result for each hypothesis indicates sig.= .002^b, .022^b, .003^b, .002^b, .002^b. The study found that accounting education had a considerable influence on accounting students' moral competencies in terms of their honesty, objectivity, competence, confidentiality and professional behavior. The study concluded that tertiary-

level accounting education is a viable strategy to develop a new generation of morally competent accountants, and that the government should therefore focus more on training of tertiary-level accounting education.

Keywords: Accounting education, moral competency and accounting profession

1. Introduction

Competence in moral matters serves as the bedrock of the accounting profession. This is because the general public places a high level of faith in the information that accountants give, which contributes to the profession's growing reputation and legitimacy. Nevertheless, the accounting profession has been plagued by a number of scandals over the past two decades, such as the scandal involving Worldcom, the scandals involving Healthsouth, Freddie mac, Lehman Brothers, and the scandal involving Satyam.

WorldCom is an American telecommunications firm that has become embroiled in one of the most serious scandals in the annals of United States history. It was able to accomplish this by making strategic use of its financial data, which resulted in a \$4 billion increase in the company's profitability before taxes. The management of the company and the chief financial officer were responsible for this fraudulent accounting conduct.

The United States Security and Exchange Commission accused one of the nation's major providers of healthcare services (Healthsouth) of engaging in fraudulent accounting practises that cost \$2.8 billion. The SEC has leveled the accusation against the corporation that it has inflated the company's income and profit. The deception was carried out with the assistance of the worker in order to grossly overstate the earnings of the firm and to entice a greater number of investors.

The Federal Housing Mortgage Loan Institute, more often referred to as Freddie mac, is an organisation that receives financial support from the federal government. Its actual profit was \$5 billion lower than what it reported. The incident was caused by a lack of accounting expertise and management of internal controls. (Sorensen & Miller, 2017)

Lehman Brothers is one of the most important investment banks in the United States. In 2008, the firm had a severe financial crisis, and it was then that it was discovered that the corporation had concealed a loan worth more than \$50 billion. Because of this, the firm became involved in one of the most significant bankruptcies in the annals of the history of the United States, despite the fact that it held assets worth more than \$600 billion at the time. (Appelbaum, Keller, Alvarez, & Bédard, 2012)

Because of these crises, the subject of reestablishing the moral integrity of the accounting profession has risen to the top of the agenda for both policy makers and practitioners in the field, as well as instructors of accounting students. One approach that has been proposed is to incorporate more ethical instruction into the accounting curriculum at every stage, from the undergraduate to the postgraduate level and even into continuing education for accountants who are already in practise. The following are some particular examples of projects now underway throughout the world with the goal of enhancing ethical instruction in accounting courses. (Gulin, Hladika, & Valenta, 2019).

Following a string of accounting scandals, the accounting board, which is part of the International Federation of Accountants, attempted to implement various cultural shifts across all industries, including the media, restaurant business, healthcare industry, and banking industry. The findings of an investigation into culture and morality have been used to help restore the confidence and integrity of accountants working in both the commercial and public sectors, and a new standard board has been established to help improve accountants' behaviours. The Certified Public Accountant of Australia (CPA Australia) is an organisation that was established to safeguard the ethical standards of accountants in Australia and to deal with any instances of misconduct or accounting scandals that may occur in Australia. The group has reached the decision that it will not put up with any instances of fraud or corruption within Australia. Any instance that has been uncovered ought to be reported to the appropriate law enforcement body that is responsible for controlling cases of fraud and corruption (Hashem, 2022).

In the meanwhile, accounting professors are of the opinion that the scandals have assisted them in highlighting the fundamental significance of accounting to their students (Holtzblatt, Foltin, & Tschakert, 2020). In order for this to have any kind of an effect, there has to be an introduction of some new relevant courses that are geared on encouraging accounting students. They have a responsibility to investigate the social, political, and ethical repercussions of the accounting decisions they make. Before graduating and entering the workforce, it is highly recommended that students complete some sort of ethics training.

When it came to responding to these accounting crises, the most important stakeholders in Nigeria's accounting profession were not left out in the cold. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria has proposed an amendment to the act and style in order to enhance higher education and reduce the likelihood of conflicts caused by unethical behaviours. This will be accomplished by instructing accountants on appropriate ethical

conduct prior to their first day on the job in businesses or other types of organisations. This is done so that the integrity and credibility of the accounting profession can be improved as a result. There has been an increase in the amount of support given by accounting organisations and businesses to accounting students in the form of teaching resources. (Moll & Yigitbasioglu, 2019)

Therefore, it stands to reason that elevating the proportion of time devoted to ethics instruction within accounting curriculum will lead to an increase in the level of moral acuity possessed by students graduating into accounting careers. However, the efficacy of a policy needs to be demonstrated by empirical data, and the purpose of this study is to give such evidence in the context of a Nigerian polytechnic called the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro.

2. Review of Literature

2.1 Accounting Education

According to Lubbe (2016) describes as "the process of transmitting knowledge about a particular subject in a structured and methodical manner, generally through formal organisations such as primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions". The transmission of accounting knowledge in an organised and methodical fashion through official educational institutions can therefore be understood to be the definition of accounting education. In the context of this study, "accounting education" refers to the understanding of accounting acquired through attendance at a polytechnic.

Universities in the United States of America began offering courses in accounting. At the time, the purpose of these courses was to make the practise of accounting more comparable to the practises of law and medicine. In the school for professional accountants, there is a high level of tolerance for the discipline that must be observed. Instead of concentrating on other types of training offered by the industry, the people who developed accounting university programmes put the majority of their attention on technical instruction and the professional accounting exams. Apprenticeship was the primary kind of instruction available to accountants throughout the latter half of the 18th century and the early years of the 19th century. The aspiring new accountant will get knowledge by seeing and taking note of the work done by the experienced accountant.

During the 1800s and 1870s, independent commercial business schools were the primary educational institutions for accounting students. The traditional custom high school focuses exclusively on freshman and sophomore level coursework. When a student has an interest in business or any other kind of commercial activity, they will sign up for classes at the commercial business school. Many young people in the country are opting to relocate

to urban areas in search of better employment opportunities now that the economy of the nation as a whole is expanding rapidly. The majority of young people who have completed either elementary or secondary schooling are required to participate in some sort of business training in order to increase their level of expertise and improve their chances of finding employment. They will gain valuable understanding about business in a relatively short amount of time at the school of business. They only needed to learn bookkeeping, mathematical computation, and uses of handwriting in order to fulfil the requirements of the syllabus. After some time had passed, they developed the typewriter as well as shorthand and typing classes. Additionally, they are able to accommodate adults who require additional accounting training. The students are allowed to choose whatever topic they would like to focus their attention on for their academic pursuits. Students in business schools tend to learn more quickly than students at other types of schools because there is less stress involved (Widyanto & Mersa, 2018).

In the decades that followed the end of the Civil War, enrollment at commercial business schools was significantly higher than enrollment at colleges. This trend continued well into the 20th century. During this time period, the economy of the nation has been expanding steadily, and during this same time period, it is possible to be successful without earning a degree or credential of any kind. At first, the higher education institution did not place a great emphasis on the accounting education; however, after seeing the success that the business school had been having, the institution made the decision to join the business school and adopt accounting education into their system. In the year 1881, the University of Pennsylvania established the very first business school, and two years later, in 1883, they offered their very first class. (Mohammed, Rohami & Azharudin, 2021).

Education in accounting is most accurately thought of as education in business. Accounting is a component of management that fosters self-understanding; it contributes to decision-making in the financial market and provides the outcome of how to manage it. Education in accounting should provide an explanation of the methodical approach to giving directives in order to enlighten accountants. Accountants will be able to acquire more knowledge and get the professional qualification that is appropriate to them thanks to the instruction that was provided to them. This education is pursued with the goals of accumulating more knowledge and elevating the level of effort put out by accountants. In order to become a great accountant, you need to be diligent in your work, have consistent training with accounting software, and have the capacity to persevere through any difficulty (Apostolou, Dorminey, Hassell & Rebele, 2018).

Therefore, the progression of accounting education ought to originate from a consistent link and interaction between the academic community and the professional accounting community. It ought not to be referred to as a conclusion in and of itself, particularly in the development of a good accountant, but rather as a means to a goal, which is to foster responsibility in both the public and private sectors of the economy. Nigeria being a fast-growing country, needs a well-developed accounting profession to facilitate her development process.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Deontology is a theory of ethics that seeks to strike a balance by arguing that regardless of whether a particular action is morally correct or wrong in the context of a given set of rules, the ethics of that action should be the basis for that decision rather than the outcome. Deontology can be thought of as a balancing theory of ethics. The origin of the term "deon" can be traced back to the Greek word "deon," which can be translated as "obligation." The morality of a person is the only thing that should be held to these standards of conduct, not their actions. The name of the German philosopher Immanuel Kant is most often used in connection with this ethical philosophy. The concept of selfhood serves as an excellent example of deontology in practice. (Islam, Seitz, Millar, Fisher, & Gilsinan, 2013)

Kant believes that the ability to reason well is what defines a person from an ethical point of view, and that selfhood organises a scope of rights and duties¹⁶. This is due to the fact that every person possesses an intrinsic dignity, which is something that is essential to uphold in equal measure by each and every individual.

According to Kant, the maxim that explains why doing the right thing is important is called reason. The majority of deontologists subscribe to the view that there are two distinct kinds of duties: perfect duties and imperfect duties. It is said that a perfect obligation is one that is obstinate. There is no way to adhere to it in a half-hearted manner; you must either butcher innocent people or not. One example of an ideal responsibility is "do not kill innocent people." It is impossible to comply with it in any other way. It is an imperfect obligation to learn about one's environment because we can devote a significant amount of time to education while still accomplishing all that we set out to do. Nevertheless, imperfect obligations have the potential to offer some form of neutral ground.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

Delligatti and Lane (2018) Conducted a study at Saudi University to assess the moral worth of accounting students and generic skills in accounting education. The survey found both

of these to be important. The study focuses on the development of general abilities in accounting education as well as the capacity and information that students are expected to gain while they are enrolled in academic programmes. A survey questionnaire was used in the process of gathering the data. According to the findings, students place a high value on all five types of generic abilities, with the ability to form moral principles being ranked as the most important. Communication, interpersonal interactions, problem solving, and critical thinking are some examples of the types of skills that fall under the category of generic talents.

This research was conducted by Islam, Seitz, Millar, Fisher, & Gilsinan, (2013). Advises and urge Malaysian accounting students to pursue their ambitions and modeling, and the environment of Malaysian accounting school suggests and encourages students to do so. The information was obtained by means of a questionnaire survey that was administered to college students who were studying accounting at the time. These analyses consisted of multiple regressions, component analysis, and t-tests using independent samples. Four inferences can be made from the results of the investigation. To begin, there may still be a lack of dedication to a profession in accounting among students who are enrolled in accounting programmes at the undergraduate level. Second, a person's innate sense of wonder can be an excellent indicator of future career choices. Thirdly, the impact of the anticipated disagreement contributes to an original discovery on the aspirational intentions of accounting students. The focus of the concluding remarks will be on the effect that the students' participation in the internship had on their future professional aspirations.

An investigation was carried out by Appelbaum, Keller, Alvarez, and Bédard, (2012) at a large university in South Africa, which showed the use of data from 4745 newly intake students of the accountancy department, for a duration of seven years from 2011-2017 to the learning performance of students at the university, and to determine the levels of skills acquired²³. The study was quite helpful in determining the various knowledge and skill components that were involved. Two primary sources were the ones that provided the information. Using an online questionnaire, the first step in the data collection process involved collecting information on demographic characteristics and skill endowments. Second, at the end of the students' last academic year, information on their overall academic performance was compiled by having them turn in their final marks for Financial Accounting. In the examination of the data, descriptive statistics were used. According to the findings, it appears that a student's character and behaviour are the primary factors that contribute to their performance in accounting.

Baker, Wick, Baker, and Wick, (2019). Conducted an investigation to see whether or not Accounting education is favourable in Korea University and the impact on the level of classroom participation shown by accounting students. Additionally, it investigates the engagement of accounting students in introductory accounting classes to see whether or not this factor contributes to efficient learning. The data for the survey came from two different individuals who attended two different universities that taught accounting principles and were among the accounting students who graduated in 2015. There were both male and female students in the set of 2015 accounting graduates. We were able to determine that males make up 53.2% of the population, while females make up 46.8%. The data also shows that 83 percent of the students are taking the accounting class for the very first time. On the other hand, we were able to enroll 76 percent of students who already have some prior knowledge of the subject²⁴. In order to demonstrate the variables brought about by the survey, a factor analysis was carried out. The conclusion that can be drawn from this is that the level of engagement shown by the students justifies the effect that the accounting education activities have.

Demir, Maroof, Sabbah Khan, and Ali, (2020), did a research work in Australia, Japan, and Sri Lanka are interested in learning more about how the accounting education systems in the aforementioned nations as well as the worldwide model for accounting education⁵ are developing. The research methodology is put into practise by way of a case study and the development of a model. According to the findings, the areas in which the accounting education systems of the three nations under examination differ from one another are the entry requirements to professional programmes, accreditation methods, and benchmark disciplinary rules.

Manfredo, Richards, Couderc, and Marchini (2006), determine whether or not culture has a significant impact on accounting education in the United States and whether or not it recognises the practical recommendations for accounting educators. In the study, three basic investigations into the role of ethics in accounting education were arranged. The first of them investigated whether or not we are aware of the influence of ethics on learning. Second, how can we establish a code of ethics for the process of education in the field of accounting? Third, what kind of implications does ethical education have for those who teach accounting? Along with the discussion of the idea for accounting educators, the author provides a combination of literary works to support their argument. The findings indicate that there is a correlation between the specific learning methods for ethics and a large number of helpful suggestions for teachers. These include problems associated with

having a short-term memory, positive and significant first encounters, and methods for fostering motivation in both students and teachers.

Bonsón and Bednárová, (2019). The purpose of the study was to accomplish two goals: the first is to determine the history of ethics education in Australian accounting education and the effects of its evolution from the years 2000 to 2012; the second is to investigate the limitations of how the head of department in an Australian university can improve the level of ethics education offered in the institution³⁰. Both of these objectives will be accomplished through the study of this research. In the accounting department, a total of 39 questionnaires were sent out to various universities in Australia that are known for their expertise in the field of degree accounting programme provision. This was done so that we could obtain additional information. As a result of the expanding role that ethics education plays in today's universities, there has been a commensurate rise in the number of universities' responses to questions concerning ethics education. On the other hand, there was a negative trend toward the increase of ethics education during the time period between the collection of data and the period data. The subpar and unsatisfactory work performance of the employees is one of the primary obstacles preventing the expansion of ethics education.

Helden and Reichard, (2018). Investigated a higher accounting education institution in southwest China to carry out an empirical study in order to facilitate the building of a teaching reform for ethics and moral worth in higher educational institutions³¹. The author's inquiry into the relationship between moral education and the learning abilities of college students will begin with the use of an empirical approach as the first stage in the investigation. The results show that the student has accepted professional and high-quality moral education, which is necessary for the student to achieve a higher level of success in the accounting practical courses. The next thing that needs to be done is to carry out a questionnaire poll in order to discover specifically which ethical and moral principles pupils accept and adhere to. The results of the study indicate that respondents place a high priority on the realization of one's own value, as well as professional ethics, teamwork, and the philosophy of lifelong learning. These five aspects of moral education are covered in accounting courses, where they receive positive feedback from students and instructors alike.

Hutahayan, (2020), The accounting programmes in France from the perspective of a respectable accounting education council³³. The research looked over a wide range of papers in order to answer the question of what exactly constitutes the standard accounting

education curriculum that is taught in France. Meetings were held with various stakeholders to understand the significance of accounting sustainability and education in the context of France; however, despite the government's need for reporting and auditing of corporate sustainability, neither of these topics is covered in great detail in the French accounting education programme that is funded by the government. As a result of this study, both the government and other relevant organisations have a better understanding of the consequences of ignoring the importance of sustainability education for accountants. In addition to this, it places an emphasis on the significance of education and training for professional accountants.

Falkenström and Höglund, (2020), Conducted research on the Islamic ethics concept. This study also investigates whether or not it is possible to incorporate Islamic ethical principles into accounting education in order to raise the ethical standards of future accountants. A questionnaire was used in conjunction with a quantitative research method to collect the necessary data. The sample for this research project consists of 195 accounting professors working at various universities in Malaysia. The findings of the study show that Islamic ethical notions were helpful in leading users toward behaviour that is consistent with Islam. The findings of a link analysis indicate that the notion of Islamic ethics has a positive and significant connection with respect to good accounting practises as well as the growth in the number of students majoring in ethical accounting. According to the findings of the study, educational institutions should place an emphasis on the moral growth of students and should consider incorporating Islamic ethical ideas into their lesson plans.

According to Alsaad, Saif-Alyousfi and Elrehail (2021), An education in accounting that is founded on Islamic ethics conducted research based on the judgement of accounting lecturers, accounting specialists, and Islamic scholars. The research approaches utilised in this study are both quantitative and qualitative. The data were acquired through the use of a questionnaire survey that was completed by 241 accounting professors hailing from 18 different academic institutions. The finding demonstrates that I accounting education that is based on Islamic ethics is vital and should be added to the curriculum, (ii) the teaching of accounting education that is based on Islamic ethics is accomplished by combining a course with the essential one in the curriculum, (iii) ethics education should be included as topics such as an understanding of the ethical burden that comes with being a professional, the traditional theories of ethics, and Islamic ethics, (iv) accounting professionals should be required to complete an ethics course, and The primary objective of this research work is to gain a better understanding of the primary proportion of environmental moral attitude, as well as to investigate the ways in which environmental education, as well as how people

behave toward one another and how they react in a specific environment, motivate business administration and accounting student. At the University of West Africa in Greece, a written question was devised in order to investigate the jury selection process for a case involving 190 business administration students. The students came from the university's departments of business administration and accounting and finance. The research was based on the fundamentals of four components that make up the environmental behaviour of the specimen. These components are the data seeking out to be reprocessed and the adult active participation. It was revealed that there is a useful connection between environmentally responsible behaviour and environmental education, and that there is an adequate relationship between environmentally responsible behaviour and ecological relation. The enthusiasm of students to turn environmental education and environmental sensitivity into a vital involvement and adult absorption behaviour was the significant conclusion. Despite the fact that the result will be very different from what other studies find, this outcome is significant.

According to Zheng and Liu, (2021), the researcher investigate the factors that have an effect on accounting students when it comes to making decisions on the best way to advance their careers³⁷. A person's capacity to choose the type of employment and the job position they choose to hold is simply referred to as their "career path." A student of accounting may wish to pursue their ambition in any of the following areas: natural inspiration, external inspiration, third parties, and career disclosure According to the findings of the previous studies, selecting a professional path is influenced by natural inspiration, external inspiration, third parties, and career disclosure. The fields of financial accounting, taxation, auditing, and finance are among the many that fall under this category. In order to collect data from the students attending a prestigious private university in Malaysia, an online survey in the form of a questionnaire was given to each individual. The accounting department of the university welcomes a sizable incoming class of freshmen and sophomores each and every year. In order to conduct an analysis of the data, the analysis system was utilised to set up 306 questions. The findings of this research lend credence to the hypothesis that undergraduate accounting students are more likely to be influenced by their own natural inspiration and professional discovery when choosing a path for their accounting careers than they are to be influenced by external influences such as those exerted by third parties.

Study conducted by Hopkins and Deepa, (2018) on how the transmission of a quality accounting information systems course influences the recognition of accounting and non-accounting students, and to check if their gap is significant enough to suggest the different

transmission of the course of accounting and non-accounting students. The purpose of this study is to investigate how the transmission of a quality accounting information systems course influences the recognition of accounting and non-accounting students. During the previous lecture weeks of the accounting information system courses at a university in Cyprus, students were given the opportunity to fill out a questionnaire. A comparison examination was carried out between the two study groups consisting of accounting students and students from other academic disciplines. According to the findings of the study, the fortunate transmission of the accounting information system course ought to improve the impact of recognising the accounting students group and raise both the profit and the impact of non-accounting. This is the proposal that has been made.

Paul Manning, (2018) investigates how the actions of the accounting sector, the economy, academic institutions, and other institutional settings all illustrate how the field of accounting has developed in South Africa. Utilizing traditional archival materials and oral biographies have been employed in the past as alternative approaches to the problem. There is evidence that the South African accounting education system has maintained its practical orientation through a network of human and non-human performers. The South African Institute of Chartered Accountants and its prior exercise have unwavering control over accounting education by advocating and providing more information on the accounting curriculum required for institution accreditation. There is a little palate that exist for strictness pertaining to academic investigation or involvement with external scholars. While the South African institute of chartered accountants declare their support on accounting study, the support is depending on its professional body congregation with the view of scholarship.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 Study's Conceptual Framework

Source: Researchers' Review (2023)

3. Methodology

Primary data was sourced through a well-structured AEDI questionnaire that was distributed using a Census Sampling Technique. The population of the study was made-up of total numbers of 242 HND2 students enrolled in Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Ogun state. The data collected by the researcher using inferential statistics and Regression model (OLS). Data was analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 26.

Due to the fact that the scope of this research is limited to accounting students at a single polytechnic, a census sampling strategy will be utilized. According to Twosa, the reliability of an instrument can be determined by looking at its cronbach's alpha and determining whether or not it is greater than 0.60.

4 Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1 Demographic Analysis

S/N.	Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age Range (years)	20 – 29	5	41.7
		30 – 39	1	8.3
		40 – 49	3	25
		50 – 59	3	25
		Above 59	-	-
2.	Gender	Male	7	58.3
		Female	5	41.7
3.	Religion	Christianity	12	100
		Islam	-	-
		Others	-	-
4.	Marital Status	Single	4	33.3
		Married	8	66.7

	Divorced	-	-
	Widow(er)	-	-
5.	Educational Qualifications		
	HND	-	-
	Bachelors	4	33.3
	Masters	6	50.0
	PhD	2	16.7
6.	Years in Service		
	0 – 5	2	16.7
	6 – 10	1	8.3
	11 – 15	1	8.3
	16 – 20	3	25.0
	21 – 25	5	41.7
	26 – 30	-	-
	Above 30		

Source: Researchers Computations, 2023

According to the results shown in Table 1, 41.7% of the lecturers surveyed were between the ages of 20 and 29, 8.3% were between the ages of 30 and 39, and 25% were between the ages of 40 and 49. Male academics had the highest presence in the study (58.3%), while female peers have 41.7%. The lecturers are all Christians. Similarly, 33.3% of Lecturers are single, while 66.7% are married. About 33.3% have a Bachelor's degree in their respective fields of expertise, 50% have a Masters degree, and 16.7% have a PhD.

25% and 41.7% of academics have used between 16 and 20 years of service and 21 to 25 years of service, respectively, while the remaining lecturers have used less than 15 years of service. Looking at the amount of years used and their academic qualifications, this indicates that the lecturers participated in the research were highly experienced and competent in their professional vocation.

4.1 Test of Hypotheses

4.1.1 Hypothesis One

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.504 ^a	.254	.180	.611

The result of the analysis as presented in the summary Table 2 indicates that there is a strong relationship between accounting education and integrity of the accounting students with correlation coefficient of 0.504 and about 25.4% variation in the integrity of the accounting students could be attributed to accounting education.

Table 3: ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.271	1	1.271	3.409	.002 ^b
	Residual	3.729	10	.373		
	Total	5.000	11			

The ANOVA Table 3) indicates an F-value of 3.409 and the p-values is less than the 5% significance level, hence the model to be derived is sufficient adequate in relating accounting education and integrity of the accounting students.

Table 4: Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	5.475	.556		9.838	.000
	Accounting Education	.508	.275	.504	1.846	.002

The coefficients Table 4 indicates that for every increase in accounting education there is about 50.8% increase in the integrity of the accounting students with t-value of 1.846 and the p-value is less than the 5% significance level. Hence, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and we then conclude that accounting education has influence on the integrity of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

4.1.2 Hypothesis Two

H_0 : Accounting education has no effect on the objectivity of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun state.

Table 5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.256 ^a	.065	-.028	.809

The model summary shows that there is a weak positive relationship between accounting education and objectivity of the accounting students with correlation coefficient of 0.256 and about 6.5% variation in the objectivity of the accounting students could be attributed to accounting education.

Table 6: ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.558	1	1.558	2.382	.022 ^b
	Residual	6.542	10	.654		
	Total	8.100	11			

In addition, the ANOVA table has an F-value of 2.382 and the p-value (0.022) is less than the 5% significance level. This is an indication that the model is sufficient and adequate in relating accounting education and objectivity of the students. The test is then affirmed to be significant.

Table 7: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	5.085	.737		6.898	.000
	Accounting Education	.305	.365	.256	.836	.022

Table 7 is the coefficient table indicating that for every unit increase in accounting education will result in about 32.2% increase in the professional competence of the students with the t-value of 0.892. the p-value is 0.003 which is less than the 5% significance level. Hence we conclude by accepting the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between accounting education and the professional competence and due care of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

4.1.3 Hypothesis III

H_0 : There is no relationship between accounting education and the professional competence and due care of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.272 ^a	.074	-.019	.800

The result as presented in Table 8 indicates that there is a very weak relationship between accounting education and professional competence and due care of accounting students enrolled as the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro. Furthermore, about 7.4% variations in professional competence and due care could be attributed to accounting education.

Table 9: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of		Mean Square	F	Sig.
		Squares	Df			
1	Regression	1.510	1	1.510	3.710	.003 ^b
	Residual	.407	10	.641		
	Total	1.917	11			

The result in Table 9 shows the F-value of 3.710 with the p-value (0.003) which is less than the 5% significance level. Hence it can be deduced that the model is significant and we can conclude that the model to be derived is sufficient and adequate at relating accounting education and professional competence.

Table 10: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	5.034	.729		6.901	.000
	Accounting Education	.322	.361	.272	.892	.003

Table 10 is the coefficient table indicating that for every unit increase in accounting education will result in about 32.2% increase in the professional competence of the students with the t-value of 0.892. the p-value is 0.003 which is less than the 5% significance level. Hence, we conclude by accepting the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between accounting education and the professional competence and due care of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

4.1.4 Hypothesis IV

H₀₄: Accounting education has no impact on the confidentiality of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

Table 11 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.101 ^a	.010	-.089	.704

In Table 11, the correlation coefficient is 0.101 which is an indication that there is a very low relationship between accounting education and confidentiality of accounting students with about 1% variation in confidentiality of the accounting students attributed to accounting education.

Table 12: ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.051	1	1.051	2.123	.002 ^b
	Residual	.949	10	.495		
	Total	2.000	11			

The result in Table 12 is the ANOVA table which indicates the F-value of 2.123 with p-value of 0.002 which is less than the 5% significance level. Hence, the test is significant and we conclude that the test is sufficient and adequate in relating accounting education and confidentiality of accounting students.

Table 12: Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	4.695	.641		7.323	.000
	Accounting Education	.102	.017	.101	5.941	.002

The result presented in table 12 indicates that for every unit increase in accounting education, there is about 10.2% increase in the confidentiality of accounting students with the F-value of 5.941. the test is significant with the p-value (0.002) less than the 5% significance level. Hence, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and we conclude that accounting education has impact on the confidentiality of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

4.1.5 Hypothesis V

H_{05} : Accounting education has no influence on the professional behaviour of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

Model Summary

Table 13: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.256 ^a	.065	-.028	.809

The result of the findings as presented in Table 13 indicates that there exists weak positive relationship between accounting education and professional behaviour of accounting students with correlation coefficient of 0.256 and about 6.5% variation in the professional behaviour of the accounting students could be attributed to accounting education.

ANOVA

Table 14: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.458	1	1.458	2.229	.002 ^b
	Residual	.542	10	.654		
	Total	2.000	11			

The ANOVA Table 14 indicates the F-value of 2.229 and the p-value of 0.002 which is less than the 5% significance level, hence, the test is significant and we conclude that the model is sufficient and adequate at relating accounting education and professional behaviour of the students.

Table 15: Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.915	.737		5.312	.000
	Accounting Education	.305	.065	.256	3.938	.002

The coefficient Table 15 indicates that for every unit increase in means of accounting education there is about 30.5% increase in professional behaviour of the accounting students with t-value of 3.938 and the p-value (0.002) which is less than the 5% significance level. Hence, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, and we conclude that accounting education has influence on the professional behaviour of accounting students enrolled at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The research goal is to critically analyse the influence of accounting education on the morale abilities of accounting students at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State. The particular goal is to examine the impact of accounting education on students' honesty, objectivity, competence, confidentiality, and professional behaviour.

The data demonstrated that accounting education had a considerable influence on students' honesty, objectivity, competence, secrecy, and professional behaviour. This is in line with the findings of Dr. Umaru Zubairu (2020).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This research investigates the effect that accounting education has on the moral capabilities of students who are majoring in accounting at the Federal Polytechnic in Ilaro, Ogun State. To a large extent, the focus is on determining the effect of accounting education on the integrity of accounting students, evaluating the relationship between accounting education and professional competence and due care, investigating the impact of

accounting education on the confidentiality of accounting students, and examining the influence of accounting education on the professional behaviour of accountants. Therefore, the study recommend that:

1. That accounting education is extremely important to the accounting profession because of the significance that it plays in the construction of nations.
2. It is imperative that the professors at the school do not let up on their efforts to remain continuously involved in instilling moral and ethical principles in the pupils.
3. The institution ought to also be concerned in knowing the professional conducts of the students after they have gained fully hired in their respective places of employment, and this should be done in a courteous manner.

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